

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF *BLEPHARIS EDULIS*, PERS., PART III. CONSTITUTION OF BLEPHARIN.

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Blepharin, $C_{18}H_{20}O_{10}$, m.p. 222° , is an optically active β -glucoside, containing 5 hydroxyl groups and gives on acid hydrolysis the aglucone, m.p. 178° .

In Part I of this series of communications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 109) the author has recorded the isolation of a crystalline bitter glucoside, *blepharin* (m.p. 222°) in addition to a colourless nitrogenous compound, identified as allantoin. Blepharin crystallises in beautiful shining colourless crystals from alcohol, acetone or water, either in the form of long rectangular plates or rhombic prisms.

It has the molecular formula $C_{18}H_{20}O_{10}$. The air-dried crystals of blepharin as obtained from rectified spirit and moist acetone have the composition $C_{18}H_{20}O_{10}$, $1\frac{1}{2} H_2O$. It is a β -glucoside and is optically active.

Anhydrous blepharin does not contain any methoxyl or ethoxyl group, but contains five alcoholic hydroxyl groups, as it forms a pentacetyl derivative, silky needles, m.p. 183° ; pentacarbethoxy derivative, silky needles, m.p. 191° after shrinking at 185° ; and a penta-*p*-nitro-benzoyl derivative, m.p. 264° after shrinking at 258° . Blepharin is saturated and does not contain any ethylenic double bond. On bromination in chloroform it chars and crystalline derivatives cannot be isolated. In blepharin aldehydic or ketonic groups are absent, as it neither gives any colouration with Schiff's reagent nor does it react with hydroxylamine, phenyl semicarbazide or phenylhydrazine. On hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid it gives the aglucone as stout prismatic needles, m.p. 178° , which is being further investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Blepharin is optically active, a sample crystallised from alcohol having $[\alpha]_D^{21.5} + 121.5^{\circ}$ (c , 0.7676). It is hydrolysed by emulsin at room temperature (30°) and is therefore a β -glucoside. [Found in air-dried sample from water: C, 47.97, 48.04; H, 5.61, 5.73; loss at 120° , 7.20. (micro) C, 47.91, 47.85; H, 5.58, 5.66; loss in vacuum at 100° (micro), 6.36, 7.10. $C_{18}H_{20}O_{10}$, $1\frac{1}{2} H_2O$

requires C, 48.12; H, 5.76; loss, 6.77 per cent]. [Found in sample dried in high vacuum at 100° (micro): C, 51.24, 51.32; H, 5.34, 5.40. Found in sample dried at 120°: C, 51.47; H, 5.42; M.W. in water (ebulioscopic), 360, 392; M.W. in phenol (cryoscopic), 360, 330. $C_{16}H_{20}O_{10}$ requires C, 51.62; H, 5.38; M.W., 372. Found in air-dried sample from alcohol: C, 48.24, 48.05; H, 5.44, 5.60; loss at 120°, 6.99. $C_{16}H_{20}O_{10}$, $1\frac{1}{2} H_2O$ requires C, 48.12; H, 5.76; loss, 6.77 per cent. Found in sample from alcohol dried at 120°: C, 51.48; H, 5.42. Found in air-dried sample from moist acetone: C, 48.85, 49.08; H, 5.50, 5.63; loss at 120°, 5.44. $C_{16}H_{20}O_{10}$, H_2O requires C, 49.22; H, 5.64; loss 4.62 per cent].

Carbethoxyblepharin was prepared by adding ethyl chlorocarbonate (13 g.) drop by drop to a solution of blepharin (1.8 g.) in pyridine (30 c.c.) and cooling the mixture in tap water. After 3 hours the product was poured into water when an oily mass separated which was washed with water and on standing overnight under water solidified and crumbled to a fine powder. It was filtered, well washed and dried in air. After two crystallisations from boiling alcohol it was obtained as beautiful, large silky needles, m.p. 161.5°. It is insoluble in boiling water, ether and petroleum ether, and is very soluble in cold pyridine, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. It is fairly soluble in cold ethyl and methyl alcohol. It is very slightly soluble in cold acetone, ethyl acetate, amyl alcohol, benzene and more in the boiling solvents. [Found: C, 50.70, 50.72; H, 5.42, 5.50; loss at 125°, 0.23; M.W. of sample dried at 120° (ebulioscopic) in ethyl alcohol, 708, 729. $C_{16}H_{15}O_{10}$ ($COOC_2H_5$)₅ requires C, 50.81; H, 5.46 per cent. M. W., 732].

Acetylblepharin.—A mixture of blepharin (2 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (17 g.) was heated under reflux at 120° for 5 hours and the cooled mixture was poured into a large volume of water; on keeping silky needles separated which were filtered, washed and dried in air, m.p. 167-168° after shrinking at 151°, yield 1.95 g. The product after two crystallisations from small quantities of ethyl alcohol was finally crystallised from hot dilute alcohol as tiny glistening needles, m.p. 183°. It is very soluble in cold alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate, pyridine, chloroform and very slightly in benzene, amyl alcohol, ether and petroleum ether. [Found in air-dried sample: C, 53.35, 53.40; H, 5.10, 5.14; CH_3CO , 36.4, 36.7; loss at 120°, 0.42; M.W. in ethyl alcohol (ebulioscopic), 581, 552. $C_{16}H_{16}O_{10}$ ($COCH_3$)₅ requires C, 53.61, H, 5.16; CH_3CO , 36.88; M.W., 581].

p-Nitrobenzoylblepharin.—To blepharin (1.6 g.), dissolved in pyridine (30 g.), finely powdered *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (10 g.) was added with vigorous shaking during the course of 3 hours. The mixture after

standing overnight was treated with excess of water when a viscous liquid separated, which on treatment with a solution of sodium bicarbonate became solid and crumbled to a fine white powder. It was filtered, washed repeatedly with water, dried in air, m.p. 254° after shrinking at 258° , yield 4.5 g. It is almost insoluble in water, hot ethyl and methyl alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate, chloroform, benzene, ether and petroleum ether but extremely soluble even in pyridine and fairly in hot dilute pyridine. On crystallisation from hot dilute pyridine after washing with water and drying in air the crystals melted at 264° after shrinking at 258° . It did not suffer any loss on drying in an air-oven at 125° for 12 hours or on heating at 110° in high vacuum over calcium chloride. [Found: C, 54.58; H, 3.29; N 6.3, 6.5. $C_{16}H_{15}O_5$ ($C_7H_4NO_4$)₂ requires C, 54.8; H, 3.14; N, 6.3 per cent].

O-Methylblepharin was obtained in poor yield by methylating blepharin (2 g.) in alkaline solution with methyl sulphate (30 g.) in the usual manner. It melted at 130° (decomp.) after shrinking at 128° .

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